

Equivalence of Time Arrows – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial equation of the coupling constants series, it is possible to reason for the reason to a unique, independent arrow of time that is one sided. The argument presented similar to independent base vectors from linear algebra.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

Suppose you had two arrows of time, the first begins with the first element in the coupling series. Define that arrow:

$$\mathcal{A}: 8 + (1) \rightarrow \mathcal{T}1 \quad (1.13)$$

And an additional arrow of time, starting from the second element the weak interaction. Define the second arrow of time:

$$\mathcal{B}: [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \mathcal{T}2 \quad (1.14)$$

The question is whether these are independent or not. Similar to procedure taken in LA, if they are scalar multiples than they are not independent and the first arrow is the base arrow for all other arrows. If you scalar multiple by three the first arrow than you reach the second:

$$[\mathcal{T}1 * 3] \rightarrow [(8 * 3) + (3)] \quad (1.15)$$

Such a construction than will yield the net variation of the term and we reached equivalence due to a scalar multiple. That is applying to each additional term in the series. It is a beautiful result because it comes to an agreement with the fact that there is only one arrow of time. to reach it we used the third representation of the primorial function, i.e. the arrow of time. the physical meaning of that result is that larger and larger clusters of fermions will cluster in an ever ending decreasing magnitude due to the same destabilizing factor, the majestic (3).

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)